

The new generation of employees' sense of job security in different environments: Impact on organizational performance

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Abstract

Switching different perspectives has a profound impact on employee performance in the new era. All kinds of management skills and social governance means must master the way of use and control the intensity of use, control the intensity of their use, and find appropriate management methods. This paper will explain the impact of job security for new-generation employees on organizational performance in different environments from different perspectives. The sense of security of employees is an important performance factor to increase the company's personnel retention rate, improve the company's performance and productivity, and increase market competitiveness. Only by mastering the fact that employees have a sense of security in different environments can they maximize their work efficiency. The perspective discussed in this paper is relatively new, and it will introduce concepts from different disciplines to discuss possible problems and ways to deal with them. Text has great practical value. It is hoped that this article can help enterprises in need improve the job security of their employees in the new era and improve human efficiency.

Keywords: *Influence of situational culture on safety and performance; Competitive relationship; Social competition; Regional competition.*

To cite this article:

Wang, W., Balsicas, N. W., & Virata, A. J. A. (2021). The new generation of employees' sense of job security in different environments: Impact on organizational performance. *The Executives*, 2, 27-40.

Introduction

Every enterprise wants to have the highest level of ability and efficiency in daily work and maintenance and constantly adjust its working methods and working environment for the best efficiency and performance. In this process, the company will always adjust some work contents, such as the policy work system, work tasks, and work environment, and will also recruit or absorb some people who can help achieve the project goals. To try their best to achieve the established performance goals, enterprises are also looking for ways to create a platform environment suitable for employees to work and grow (Wang, 2017), to ensure that employees can be a major reason for achieving goals in this regard. However, with the development of information technology and Internet technology, new employees with personalities appear in society (Wang et al., 2022). The new generation of employees (Warner & Zhu, 2018) has gradually become an important part of the current society, and relying on their high-level knowledge, high-level skills, innovation, and creativity, they have become a variety of current enterprise organizations. The core staff of the group has had a profound impact on the development of the current enterprise (Xiao, 2018).

Employee job security is a key indicator that is currently more important in enterprises (Newman et al., 2019), which mainly develops with the reform and development of enterprises and, in the process, affects employees' commitment and attitude towards the enterprise, thereby affecting the overall organizational performance of a firm (Al-Dalahmeh et al., 2018). When employees have a greater sense of job security, they will make greater efforts in their own work to double their work tasks and do everything possible to achieve themselves and the company (Valackiene et al., 2021). Behaviors like this tend to improve the performance of the company. In other words, employee job security will directly affect individual work behavior (Yousef, 2017), thereby affecting the overall performance of the rewarding enterprise. Of course, we can also say that when an employee lacks a sense of job security, they will definitely not treat the company with a wholehearted attitude. Up to now, the impact of employees' job security on corporate organizational performance has been concerned by many scholars, who have tried to establish the relationship between the two (Cao & Mu, 2017) and put forward corresponding processing principles to make enterprises better deal with it.

This study will consider the impact of employees' job security on organizational performance in different environments. Is there a normal moderating effect between the two? Or the interaction of job security on organizational performance (Cao & Mu, 2017)? We set employee job security as a basic variable, which can also be said to be an incentive (Lu et al., 2017), through which we study changes in organizational performance. Of course, all of this research is based on a new generation of employees. Therefore, this paper attempts to analyze the impact of the new generation of employees' job security on organizational performance in the four working environments that the new generation of employees may be in and to think about the possible impact. How should enterprises deal with these impacts?

This study describes the work stress environment for the new generation of employees' sense of job security regarding the impact on organizational performance (Ghasemi et al., 2018), that is, the impact of employees in a high-pressure environment and a low-pressure environment; This will later elaborate on the impact of high and low contextual cultural environments on the new generation of employees' job security on organizational performance (Zhang et al., 2019); This research explains the impact of job competition environment on organizational performance on the new generation of employees' job security (Anwar & Abdullah, 2021), that is, employees are in a perfect competitive environment and an imperfect competitive environment, as well as in the regional environment; finally, based on the analysis of the impact on employees in the above four environments, we will consider the impact of the new generation of employees, how the enterprise should address the impact brought about in this process.

Literature Review

New Generation of Employees

The new generation of employees is mainly a part of the population that appears with the development of the economic era. There is no complete and unified concept for this, but in academia, scholars often use age and background to define it. Born after 1980, a generation appeared with the development trend of the Internet and economic globalization.

The new generation of employee renewals is a group with a distinctly different style than previous generations of workers, with different personalities and values. In this study, a replacement employee is defined as the post-80s, post-90s, post-00s, and other human groups entering the workplace. We can obviously find many characteristics in them, such as strong self-awareness, a high level of knowledge, a unique career outlook, loyalty to their lifestyle, a willingness to challenge new things, and other characteristics. These characteristics will affect their job security as an important factor.

Characteristics of New Generation Employees

1. Strong self-awareness and distinct personality. Many of the new generation of employees have only one child in their own family or a few siblings, which makes them surrounded by their neighbors and relatives since childhood. Under such an environment, the new-age employee will become more self-aware, and more of them will choose to develop themselves in the progress of society. The concept of individual independence, independent thinking, and independent behavior is gradually accepted by the new generation of employees who are looking for personal development. This process shows the independence and autonomy of employees in the new era.

2. Have a high level of ability, have the spirit of innovation. The new generation of employees is accompanied by the development of the Internet, and they were born in the era of knowledge revival and knowledge innovation. And with the implementation of education, While the new generation of employees is receiving education, their own knowledge level, ability to respond, and innovation ability have been greatly improved.

3. Changes in professional attitudes. With the continuous development of society and the economy, enterprises have gradually simplified social functions, and the concept of new-generation employees has also changed. In such an environment, career discrimination against employees in the new era is more inclined toward the improvement of personal interests and abilities. When the existing jobs do not have a good operating space, they may choose to look for new and better jobs.

4. Be true to your way of life, not your job. The new-age employee believes that work is not the whole of life. They want to do some challenging and interesting work, but they do not want it to be too hard. They hope that life can be separated from work and that they can enjoy leisure and socializing. For the new-age employee, the quality of life has become a more important factor than the quality of work.

5. Like to challenge new things, dare to face difficulties, not good at compromise. At this stage, the new generation of employees is always looking for jobs that can improve themselves, are challenging, can realize their own value, can stimulate their potential, and have a certain degree of autonomy. A job that can be challenging all the time is more attractive to a new generation of employees than a regular job. From the perspective of social phenomena, the decrease in young civil servants further confirms this point. Doing the same thing day after day will eventually tire the new generation of employees.

6. Like to express themselves, eager to be recognized by others. New-age employees like to express themselves at work, showing the best spirit and state to everyone around them. The achievements and results they want to achieve are expected to be seen by others. Of course, they also want to be praised by leaders and bosses. This phenomenon is especially prominent among employees in the new era. For the new-age employee, praise and honor are great encouragement and support for them and will have a great motivating effect. But once your performance and achievements are not discovered or praised, you will become frustrated and lost.

Job Security

According to Hobfoll (2001), the Conservation of Resources (COR) model is a stress model about humans. It is believed that when people are in a certain environment, individuals have the opportunity and ability to strive for or maintain themselves to obtain things. When an individual can obtain or maintain a certain state at the current stage and in the future, the corresponding psychological activities are collectively referred to as a sense of security.

Based on the COR model, we can analyze four situations that have an impact on employees' job security. First, you are gaining or losing valuable resources; second, you have gained or lost some things with certain benefits; third, the degree of clarity of the connection with yourself and valuable things; fourth, whether you can stay for a long time and have something of value. Therefore, the employee's sense of job security should be based on a comprehensive understanding of the company's resources currently occupied by them and what they may gain or lose in the future. As a comprehensive cognition, employees' job security is affected by personal characteristics and has obvious uniqueness.

Research on employees' job security mainly focuses on the following two aspects: the first aspect, whether employees can obtain valuable things (expected things) stably from the enterprise and whether the enterprise can meet the expectations of employees; the second aspect, whether employees are competent for the requirements of the enterprise and whether the enterprise can provide returns. The content of employees' job security should include: the development status of the enterprise; whether the work content is stable; whether the career development meets expectations; whether the job is secure; and whether the enterprise is reliable.

The Link Between Employee Job Presence and Organizational Performance

The personal performance of employees is an important factor in determining organizational performance (Obiekwe & Obibhunun, 2019), so when employees are satisfied with their current jobs, they will contribute their best efforts at work, and these efforts will often improve the overall performance of the enterprise. For the research on organizational performance, many scholars have already made some research results, but most of the research directions are factors affecting the organizational performance of enterprises.

Pang and Lu (2018) proposed four dimensions that affect organizational performance, including job achievement, compensation incentive system, job security system, and overall work environment, and analyzed the impact of the four dimensions on organizational performance through questionnaires and impact effects. Varma (2017) once proposed the impact of incentive strategies on organizational performance. Through the analysis of different incentive strategies, it was concluded that employee status has an important impact on corporate profits (organizational performance), and incentive strategies are the main reason that directly affects employee status. Of course, in addition to the above list, there are many other factors that affect organizational performance: job security (Pacheco et al., 2020), employee personal reasons (Diamantidis & Chatzoglou, 2018), and work environment (Gallardo-Gallardo et al., 2020).

This paper mainly studies the impact of job security for employees in the new era on organizational performance in different environments. The key lies in the relationship between employee job security and organizational performance. Employee job security is also an important factor in improving performance. Only by establishing a sound security mechanism can employees improve their performance capabilities. The main performance chart can be seen below:

Figure 1. The link between employee job presence and organizational performance

With the development of society, the growth opportunities and educational approaches of employees in the new era have undergone great changes. The social competition brought about by the popularization of education is becoming more and more intense. As a result, people generally lack security, and job stability and high welfare have become an inevitable pursuit. But there are other considerations beyond these two main factors. If enterprises want to seize the work enthusiasm of the new generation of employees, it is an inevitable choice to improve employees' sense of job security. An insecure enterprise will cause a large outflow of talent from the enterprise.

The Company Based On the Pressure Environment of Employees in the New Era

The impact of high-pressure environment on new-generation employees' stress, job security and organizational performance

The high-pressure environment in this article refers to the establishment of key performance indicators (KPIs) for employees that are higher than the same industry in the business process of enterprises and to establishing a spirit of struggle and enterprising in the corporate culture. This is to keep employees in a state of high concentration at all times (at least superficially). Companies with high-pressure environments have a great negative impact on newcomers' sense of security, but employees who can withstand it can usually perform well. A more representative example is the "996" (working 9:00 every day and 9:00 at the end of work six days a week) work system in Chinese Internet companies. In such a high-pressure working environment, following the torrent of times, China's Internet companies have made great strides in the face of the market and development dividends and once made a large number of rich people.

When there are predecessors as role models, employees in the new era will find that as long as they work hard, they can achieve the same success as their predecessors when facing a high-pressure environment. With the continuous enrichment of material life, people's pursuit of life will not stop, as will the amount of wealth. They began to pay attention to the quality of life, and public opinion and the Chinese government also began to oppose the overtime culture. This is an inevitable choice for social development, and the same type of social structure can be found in Western developed countries. At the same time, some companies in China also found similar problems and began to gradually reduce the company's pressure environment.

The impact of low-pressure environment on new-generation employees' stress, organizational performance and job security

The low-pressure environment in this article refers to working without a challenging performance plan. In the working environment, the company will give employees greater freedom to play. By delegating power and motivating employees to create, so as to improve employee safety, improve employee happiness index, and work happily, the low-voltage environment will inhibit the development of the company to a certain extent, and in the face of a relatively fiercely competitive environment, there will often be an unfavorable situation to deal with. The main reason is that the low-stress environment will stimulate people's laziness, which makes them lack a positive attitude in the face of crises.

The impact of the low-pressure environment on the performance of new employees is also limited. When facing a low-pressure environment, the retention rate of employees can be greatly improved, and the sense of security of employees can be increased. The samples of companies that are doing well in the middle are Kingston and Fat Donglai. These companies are working hard to create a comfortable working environment and salary for their employees. Relatively speaking, each new employee's emotional and work enthusiasm for the company is also increasing. The level of recognition for this job will be higher.

Companies in a low-stress environment mostly appear to be companies with good corporate profitability and imperfect internal assessment systems. While creating a low-pressure working environment, these companies also provide good help for their own talent team building. Pursuing a happy and dignified job is an important reason for every employee in the new era to choose a job. Only enough responsibility for employees can be reflected in the return of employees to the company.

The transformation of high-voltage companies into low-voltage companies is the inevitable logic of the company's development. The strongest qualities of human nature are stability and comfort. The same is true of social development. In capitalist countries, resources are often in the hands of a few people, but in China, social stability and improving people's quality of life are given top priority. Therefore, the excessively high-pressure environment will gradually withdraw from the labor market in China.

Relationship Between High and Low Situational Cultural Environment and Employees' Job Security in the New Era on Organizational Performance

High situational culture and employees' job security in the new era on organizational performance

Since traditional business administration has little research on high-situation culture, this article first explains the general content of the concept. The interpretation of the concept in this article is the embodiment of my subjective consciousness, which may be different from the standard interpretation. High-situation culture mainly focuses on situation rather than content in social relationships and focuses on a highly valued social relationship. The high-situation culture expresses emotions more implicitly, showing that phrases cover high information in explanation and context (e.g., idioms, ancient poems). High-situation culture is more common in the Confucian cultural circle centered on China.

Companies with high contextual cultures are mostly found in Asian countries. The company conveys its business philosophy by describing the company's mission, vision, and values, so that employees pay attention to the environment that grows with the company. Companies with a high contextual culture increase the cohesion within the enterprise through a series of management methods, usually team building, to increase organizational relationships and the familiarity of personnel in various departments. In this way, it can promote employees' recognition of the company's culture and let employees realize that people who have common topics and work together in the company can greatly enhance employees' sense of security.

Relatively speaking, the implementation of a high-situation culture is an exchange of security for employees to give in a certain private space and private information. However, in the case of non-blood relations, the social pressure brought about by the excessive transfer of private space is also huge. Once the high-situation culture crosses the threshold, employee performance and security will decline. This decline is almost irreversible. The collective analysis can refer to the following figure:

Figure 2. Relationship between high situational culture and employees' job security

Most of the companies with a high contextual culture appear in R&D and sales companies, and the reason is not complicated. Mainly, new employees need personnel to guide and teach them when they carry out their work. In this way, there will be dependence on superiors or old employees. The same upward path begins when new employees become old people. The greater the dependence on people, the more the environment in which they live will shift to a high-situation culture.

Low-situation culture on new generation employees' job security on organizational performance

The main performance of low-situation culture is the opposite of the concept of high-situation culture. It focuses on content rather than situation in communication. Low-situation culture does not pay much attention to interpersonal communication. More emphasis is placed on the concept of self; most of the communication and communication with people have certain practical value; the content of communication is relatively direct; and it is impossible to implicitly express what you want to express.

The low-situation culture mainly appears in the western world. In enterprise management, it mainly focuses on the method of doing things and the correct procedure instead of emphasizing the impact of personal relationships on the enterprise. Companies with a low-situation culture will have a large number of format documents, such as employee management manuals, employee execution manuals (standard operating procedure manuals), and other rules that focus on doing things. Its main product, the office automation system, is an important contribution of low-context culture to management.

However, compared to companies with a high-context culture, a low-context culture overemphasizes correct processes and operations. This will lead to a reduction in employees' sense of identity with the company. When a sense of identity cannot be found in the company, it will greatly reduce the sense of security among employees. As a result, the retention rate of personnel has been reduced, and more extreme cases are similar to Foxconn jumping off a building. Specifically, as shown in the figure below:

Figure 3. Relationship between low situational culture and employees' job security

Most companies with a low-scenario culture appear to be production-oriented enterprises that need to deal with problems encountered in the production process through a large number of rules and processes. The main characteristics of production-oriented enterprises are the large composition of personnel and the relatively slow technological and cultural innovation. Enterprise problems can only be managed effectively by relying on a large number of rules.

The Impact of Job Competitive Environment on Organizational Performance and Job Security for the New Generation of Employees

Perfect Competitive Environment

The perfect competitive environment in this paper refers to the situation in which the competition between various positions in the company is relatively fierce. This includes the competition of positions and the competition of interests. To improve the work enthusiasm of the company's employees, many companies will implement the management method of perfect competition to differentiate the collective behavior of some employees. Its main performance is to reward employees with top internal performance, allow employees to conduct PK competitions, and hold swearing-in meetings. Through these management methods, the awareness of competing for interests in the face of interests is formed before employees.

The environment of perfect competition will inhibit the work performance of new employees to a certain extent, especially in this contemporary labor market environment. It will also reduce the sense of security of new employees. Because it is a perfect competitive relationship, in addition to cooperating with each other, colleagues mainly compete with each other, which will lead to a decrease in work efficiency. When a team is in a perfectly competitive environment, there must be more negative than positive effects on the growth of newcomers. Most companies in a perfectly competitive environment are sales-oriented rather than service-oriented, and such companies tend to focus on short-term gains rather than long-term gains. The survival time of these companies is generally less than five years because a perfectly competitive environment will greatly consume employees' work energy.

Imperfect Competitive Environment

The imperfect competitive environment in this paper means that in the process of business operation, the distribution of the benefits of the enterprise is mainly in accordance with the established rules of the enterprise. Individual gains and team gains are not strongly correlated with the actual workload. Imperfect competition mostly occurs in judgmental firms, which place more emphasis on the procedural convenience brought by mutual coordination than on individual competence. The imperfect competitive environment can effectively improve the cooperation ability of various departments, groups, and individuals, especially creative companies, which has great positive significance.

The Impact of the Regional Environment on the Job Security of the New Generation of Employees on Organizational Performance

The pressure that the regional environment brings to employees' sense of security is the most important of all factors. The regional environment in this paper mainly refers to the demands of employees for a sense of security in a specific area. It is mainly divided into first-tier cities, second-tier cities, and low-income and low-consumption cities. Different regional environments have different needs for talent. When the urbanization process is not over, the city's attraction to labor is an inevitable market choice. But if a city's income level is low but spending is high, there will be a brain drain. The main difficulties encountered by employees in first- and second-tier cities in the new era are as follows:

1. Buying a house in big cities is more difficult. Difficulty in buying a house is one of the problems faced by the new generation of employees, especially the new generation of employees working in first-tier cities. On the one hand, they have to endure overtime at work every day; life is difficult to imagine.

What is certain is that housing prices in first-tier cities have exceeded the affordability of ordinary people. In fact, according to the latest statistics, the housing price-to-income ratio in first-tier cities across the country in 2019 is generally above 20, which means that it takes 20 years to buy a house in a first-tier city without eating or drinking. From the time of graduation from university, the new generation of employees will have to be 40 years old when they want to buy a house. Logically speaking, buying a house at this age is not bad, but the problem is that houses in China are closely related to many things, such as when you get married, you must have a house, and when your children go to school, you must also have a house. Therefore, the new generation of employees simply cannot wait to buy a house when they are 40 years old. This is one of the reasons why it is difficult for young people in first-tier cities to buy a house.

2. Difficulty for children to go to school.

Reason 1: There is a shortage of degrees. Difficulty going to school has become a common problem in almost every country in the Confucian cultural circle. The emphasis on education in the Confucian cultural circle is engraved in the cultural genes. The profound educational culture leads people to have an unimaginable pursuit of high-quality education. After all, high-quality educational resources are limited, and the Confucian cultural circle attaches great importance to education. As a result, a large number of people began to compete for good degree opportunities, and a unique concept of school district housing appeared in China. A good degree of opportunity can give a huge boost to local house prices. The result is that people's competitive pressure increases. When young people in the new era are considering the education of the next generation, they may choose areas with less educational pressure in the face of competitive pressure.

Reason 2: High tuition fees. After the implementation of compulsory education in China, tuition fees for basic education have been gradually reduced. But if you want to compete for better educational resources, you need to make a lot of investments in education. Compulsory education can only provide the knowledge and cognitive part of basic education, and it has also become an important competition track for the current competitive quality. All competitions require a significant investment of money and resources. Faced with the high tuition fees in the first and second tiers, when considering market competition, the new generation of employees often chooses not to have children or to have fewer children. This will bring an increase in the insecurity of employees in the new era to big cities and will also become an important reason for the new generation of employees to run away from home.

Reason 3: Settlement problem. The household registration system has always been the main factor restricting the rise of the vast peasant class in China. Since the founding of New China, through the unique household registration system and the Chinese people's unique deep feelings for local culture, the role of farmers in the city has only been to provide cheap labor to ensure the normal operation of the city. With the advancement of urbanization and the general improvement of people's education level, there is a higher demand for the working environment. The new generation of young people began to gradually weaken this dependence on their hometown and chose cities where they began to consider long-term life and work when choosing a career and retirement.

The issue of household registration will still be a major factor hindering the development of young people. The safety of employees in the new era will be greatly reduced. When their own hard work is not recognized, most young people who have struggled will choose cities with low consumption and low income. This will greatly compress the enthusiasm of young people to struggle. When they are not recognized, their children can only choose to return to the place of household registration when they go to school. This phenomenon will gradually consume the residual value of young people and make them lose their motivation to struggle.

3. Difficulty settling in. With the development of the economy and society, the new generation of employees advocates living in the city, but to be able to live in the city, all they have to do is settle down. But relative to work, settling down is a major issue that has to be considered. Here we take Beijing as an example and analyze the difficulty of settlement according to Beijing's 2018 settlement policy.

In 2018, a total of 124,657 people in Beijing declared points to settle down, and the list of Beijing points to settle down has been announced. In accordance with the principle of equal points and equal settlement, the planned scale of settlement is 6,000, and the corresponding minimum score is 90.75 points. The actual public list is 6,019 people. The high threshold of Beijing's points settlement policy is second to none among domestic cities. Taking social security deposits as an example, Beijing has been the most stringent for seven consecutive years; considering the first batch of 124,000 people in Beijing who applied for points and 6,019 people finally passed, the "pass rate" of Beijing's points settlement in 2018 was only 4.8%. Among all the people passing through, there are more than 600 people born in the 1980s, accounting for about 1/10. Therefore, if the new generation of employees wants to take root in another city, the issue of settling down must be the most important, because settling down means truly integrating into the city and enjoying its policies and benefits, such as education, economy, and culture.

4. Difficulty in employment and low income. Today, the cost of living and pressure are increasing, and the employment situation is still severe. For the new generation of employees, the number of employees is increasing every year, and there are more and more competitors. Many new generation employees have high expectations for their first job, with a monthly salary of 8,000 yuan, which is a job they like in a city they like. *"But when I actually look for a job, I realize that I have very little choice. Either I am too picky, or I have insufficient ability. The job I want but I don't have the ability."*

In fact, when it comes to employment difficulties and low income, we have to mention the watershed of income exceeding 10,000 yuan. In this society, the false rumor that everyone's monthly salary exceeds 10,000 yuan has filled many new-generation employees with illusions. Along with social anxiety and a sense of urgency for employment, the new-generation employees have strong expectations for high salaries and believe that a monthly salary of more than 10,000 yuan is the most satisfying thing to do.

According to data, 70% of the new generation of employees have a salary of less than 6,000. Such a salary level is likely to be a problem for those who go to first-tier cities to support themselves, because the rent is likely to occupy their own income. *"It is difficult to survive in first-tier cities, but I do not want to stay in second- and third-tier cities. I feel that there is no opportunity for development. I thought that a job with a monthly salary of 5,000 would be easy to find, but I turned around and submitted the resumes of several companies and found that even a company with a monthly salary of 3,000. You have to weigh whether you want to be yourself."*

5. Weak human feelings. The first consideration for companies in first- and second-tier cities is how to solve the above five problems encountered by the new generation of employees. Companies that can address these issues can greatly improve their employees' job security and their ability to perform. Every young person who has worked hard and moved from other places to big cities has almost the same yearning for a new life. Only by creating a company environment in which they work hard and reap the rewards can we greatly stimulate employees' organizational performance capabilities.

Compared with big cities like first- and second-tier cities, the low-income and low-consumption regional environment provides comfort to the new generation of employees but also increases complaints about low incomes. The living class in small cities is relatively rigid, close to the environment of high-scenario culture. Work and life require contact with a large number of people, and the people around them will be very familiar. There are far fewer job opportunities in small cities than in big cities, and there are few jobs to choose from. It is also difficult to develop professional skills in small cities.

Research Novelty

Employees have always been the most important part of an enterprise and have a decisive impact on its development. The professional behavior and performance of employees are the direction that every enterprise pays more attention to. Up to now, there are few academic studies on the impact of employee security on organizational performance, and the fields involved are relatively few, mainly focusing on factors that can affect employees' job security, such as employee job satisfaction and compensation management. However, it can be found that with the progress of the times, more and more new-generation employees with distinctive characteristics are participating in the workplace, showing ideas different from those of the original employees. It can be said that the arrival of the new generation of employees affects the management of employees in enterprises. It also affects the original research results in academia. With this change, the impact of employee security on enterprises has been studied by more and more scholars, and the new generation of employees has gradually become one of the concerns. Therefore, this paper explores the impact of the new generation of employees' job security on organizational performance from a new perspective. At the same time, it introduces concepts from different disciplines to study employees in four environments (stress environment, high and low situational cultural environment, job competition environment, regional environment) and find appropriate management methods to effectively improve the job security of the new generation of employees.

Conclusions

The humanistic environment, social environment, and company cultural environment are all important factors that affect employees' sense of security. Only by doing a good job of matching the company culture with the employee's personality can employees maximize their organizational performance capabilities. If you rashly introduce a company culture and management system that does not belong to yourself, it will only bring harm to the company.

Figure 4. Amoeba Management Model

Taking the “Amoeba Management” model as an example, when Mr. Kazuo Inamori created and used this method, he was able to create a business miracle under traditional Japanese cultural values combined with the export-oriented strategy in Japan. Through the so-called improvement of the original amoeba system, a lot of corporate training consulting institutions have emerged in China. Forcing the Amoeba system into an unsuitable enterprise system has led to a large number of failed cases (Inamori, 2013). The management methods of low-context culture represented by McKinsey and IBM have a good complementary effect in the face of China-centered countries with high-context culture. Its most representative company is China's Huawei. The management approach of a low-context culture focuses on steps and processes.

In the face of high-situational cultures, management methods have played a very good complementary role. When the company competes with the opposite company, the pressure on its employees is also the key to determining the company's competitiveness. Whether it is a high-voltage competitive environment or a low-voltage competitive environment, in the face of corporate competition, only by adjusting the appropriate corporate competitive environment can external competitiveness be improved. The transition from a high-pressure environment to a mortgage environment is an inevitable course of enterprise development, as is the country. By adjusting the pressure of competition and gradually increasing employees' sense of security in the company, thereby improving performance capability, this is a management philosophy that every manager should learn.

As the overtime culture of "996,007" began to be criticized and questioned, China's leading companies led the team to gradually cancel the management method of high-pressure environments. Begin to switch to low-pressure management. Among them are the popularization of the law, the reduction of the company's stable demand for overtime (mainly due to the occurrence of a large number of invalid overtimes), and the pursuit of quality life by employees in the new era.

Adapting to the contemporary historical environment and paying attention to employees' thinking about the high-pressure environment in the new era are the main problems that every enterprise manager has to face. Job competition is an important indicator of a company's corporate culture. Perfect competition and imperfect competition have no corresponding advantages or disadvantages. Only to find a competitive relationship suitable for the development of one's own enterprise and to continuously improve it in the process of operation is an important philosophy of operating an enterprise.

Perfect competition can quickly help enterprises open up the market environment. At the same time, high income and high pressure will inevitably bring good expectations of future income to employees in the new era, as well as emotional problems of lack of security in the face of competition. The consideration of imperfect competition is mainly for civil servants, state-owned enterprises, and some private enterprises with little competition pressure. Generally, there are certain judgments and channel-first-mover advantages. In the face of incomplete competition, you can focus your energy on your work, and you don't have to worry about decision-making mistakes caused by excessive competition.

The regional environment is an important factor for employees to consider when choosing a job, finding employment, and keeping a job in the new era. Taking China as an example, from first-tier cities to impoverished areas, the siphon effect of cities will gradually drain the high-quality labor in impoverished areas. Whether it is manual work or mental work, it has never been a good choice for impoverished areas in the face of high-latitude cities.

With the development of the Internet economy, the working environment of employees in the new era has gradually shifted from offline to online development. Since China is a high-scenario country, both social pressure and family pressure do not require face-to-face interaction on the Internet platform, which also lays a good foundation for employees in the new era to escape from big cities. With the gradual completion of the urbanization process, more young people will return to their birthplaces, start their working careers with the help of the Internet, or rely on family paths. In the face of this situation, companies in need can completely transfer most of the low-tech labor-intensive industries to underdeveloped areas and deploy regional markets in less developed areas in advance.

Social competition is an important consideration hidden in regional and company cultures. The competition between the sexes mentioned above is the fundamental relationship of social competition. Effectively resolving gender antagonism, increasing the rights and interests of the unequal party, and preventing class antagonism between the genders is an important direction to improve the job security of the new generation of employees. By constantly choosing to adjust the company's cultural environment and correctly grasping the competitive relationship, the company can improve the productivity of its employees.

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